

Fitting of data: JBW-NP-P-V5 2021-02-18_09-22-57
 $0.0185 \leq q \text{ (nm}^{-1}\text{)} \leq 25.1$
 Active parameters: 1, ranges: 1
 Background level: 0.068 ± 0.00158
 (Scaling factor: $3.2e+33 \pm 2.43e+31$)
 Timing: 10 repetitions of 52.6 ± 2.58 seconds

Range $1.500e-10$ to $1.500e-07$, vol-weighted
 totalValue: $2.241e-04 \pm 5.438e-07$
 mean: $3.361e-09 \pm 6.495e-12$
 variance: $7.159e-19 \pm 6.412e-20$
 skew: $1.501e+00 \pm 5.296e-01$
 kurtosis: $1.403e+01 \pm 3.876e+00$

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